

Synthesis of some New 7-Substituted-aminomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonamides for Biological Interest

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7-Aryl (or alkyl)aminomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonamide derivatives (2-5) have been prepared by the Mannich reaction on 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonylchloride with primary and secondary amines. The compounds were verified by elemental and spectral data, and were biologically screened.

THE substituted-8-hydroxyquinolines have been reported as potential amoebicides¹⁻⁴. Moreover 7-substituted-aminomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acids⁵ have been found to exhibit remarkable antibacterial activity. Therefore we have synthesised a new series of 7-substituted-aminomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonamide derivatives (2-5) to evaluate their biological activities.

Interaction of 8-hydroxyquinoline with chloro-sulphonic acid afforded 5-sulphonylchloride derivative (1). The title compounds were prepared through Mannich reaction according to the usual procedure^{3,4} and identified by elemental analysis, ir and electronic spectral data. The uv spectra (methanol) displayed $\pi-\pi^*$ transition bands due to phenyl and heterocyclic rings around 260-275s, 320-325 and 360-380br nm (broad) and the ir spectra showed bands at 3 100-3 400 (NH), 1 310-1 380, 1 130-1 150 (SO₂) and 2 800-2 900 cm⁻¹ (CH₂).

The nmr spectra (DMSO) of 3a revealed signals at δ 2.7 (2H, s, CH₂), 3.4 (10H, s, N-piperidine), 4.3 (10H, s, SO₂-N-piperidine) and 7.2-8.9 (5H, m, quinoline). The nmr spectra (DMSO) of 2a revealed signals at δ 1.85 (1H, s, NH), 2.45 (2H, s, CH₂), 3.8 (10H, s, 2x Ph) and 7.2-8.7 (5H, m, quinoline).

The bactericidal activities of the selected compounds (at concentration 5 μ g per disc) were determined by usual disc assay method against *Staph. aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *E. coli* and *Serratia sp.* using normal nutrient agar containing 1 g yeast per lit. The bacterial suspension was prepared by adding 1 ml sterile distilled water to a 24 h old culture of the test organism grown on nutrient agar slant. Most of them showed remarkable bactericidal activity against *P. aeruginosa* (2a, d, k, 3a, b, 4b) and a promotion effect towards *M. luteus* (2b, c, g, h, k, 3a, b, 4b). Some of them showed a promotion

effect towards *S. aureus* (2h, k). It was also noticed that replacement of the sulphonamide group by heterocyclic nucleus or alkyl group enhances the activity as in case of compounds 3b, 4b, 5a. From our previous studies, it is also worthy to note that replacement of 5-sulphonamide group by 5-sulphonic group⁶ induced differences in the bactericidal activity depending on the type of substituent and bacterial species used.

- 2
2a, R=C₆H₅
b, R=p-NO₂-C₆H₄
c, R=p-COOH-C₆H₄
d, R=p-OOH₂-C₆H₄
e, R=1-C₁₀H₇
f, R=2-C₅H₄N
g, R=CH₃
h, R=C₄H₉
k, R=COOHCH₂

- 3
3a; X=CH₂
3b; X=O

- 4
4a; R=CH₃
4b, R=C₂H₅

- 5
5a; R=CH₃
5b; R=C₂H₅
5c, R=C₄H₉

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on an Unicam SP 200 G spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched silica cells and

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (2-5)*

Compd. no.	Colour	M.p °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Spectral data ir $\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	$\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ)
2a	Greenish yellow	325d	60	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ S	2 850(CH ₂), 3 400(NH), 1 380, 1 120(SO ₂)	270(5.9), 380(3.9)
2b	Brownish yellow	275	55	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₇ N ₃ S	2 900(CH ₂), 3 350(NH), 1 310, 1 156(SO ₂)	265(5.5), 375(4.6)
2c	Greenish yellow	334	50	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₇ N ₃ S	2 900(CH ₂), 3 400(NH), 1 690(CO), 1 380, 1 310(SO ₂)	258(6.8), 375(4.9)
2d	Reddish brown	285	60	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₈ N ₃ S	2 900(CH ₂), 3 400(NH), 1 380, 1 120(SO ₂)	265(6.28), 320(5.3), 390(4.45)
2e	Greenish	295	65	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ O ₈ N ₃ S	2 850(CH ₂), 3 400(NH), 1 380, 1 140(SO ₂)	260(6.7), 320(4.32), 370(4.06), 390(3.9)
2f	Greenish	268	50	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ O ₈ N ₃ S	2 850(CH ₂), 3 400(NH), 1 380, 1 120(SO ₂)	270(5.50), 375(3.52)
2g	Grey	299	60	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ S	2 800(CH ₂), 3 100(NH), 1 320, 1 140(SO ₂)	258(4.4), 320(3.0), 360(2.93)
2h	Buff	280	70	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	2 850(CH ₂), 3 300(NH), 1 350, 1 140(SO ₂)	260(4.2), 325(3.19), 355(2.62)
2k	Yellow	235	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₇ N ₃ S	2 840(CH ₂), 3 100(NH), 1 720(CO), 1 310, 1 130(SO ₂)	258(5.69), 320(3.69), 510(3.67)
3a	Buff	280	70	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	2 870(CH ₂), 1 340, 1 150(SO ₂)	255(6.46), 320(3.1), 370(2.43)
3b	Pink-buff	291	50	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃ S	2 800(CH ₂), 1 340, 1 120(SO ₂)	265(5.32), 325(3.81), 370(3.47)
4a	White	320	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ S	2 800(CH ₂), 1 340, 1 120(SO ₂)	265(5.79), 325(3.91), 375(3.86)
4b	Pink-buff	271	60	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	2 900(CH ₂), 3 400(NH), 1 310, 1 120(SO ₂)	265(6.85), 325(4.51), 375(4.51)
5a	Pink-buff	305	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ S	2 800(CH ₂), 3 300(NH), 1 340, 1 120(SO ₂)	265(5.68), 325(4.03), 380(4.03)
5b	Buff-grey	258	60	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₃ S	2 800(CH ₂), 3 280(NH), 1 340, 1 120(SO ₂)	265(5.51), 320(4.05), 380(3.66)
5c	White	265	60	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₃ S	2 800(CH ₂), 3 280(NH), 1 320, 1 140(SO ₂)	

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA* OF (2-5)

	S sp	P. a	P. v	S. a	B. c	M. l
2a	—	13 (p.i.)	—	—	—	—
2b	—	—	—	—	—	(p.e.)
2c	—	—	—	—	—	(p.e.)
2d	—	12 (p.i.)	—	—	18 (p.i.)	—
2g	—	—	—	(p.e.)	—	(p.e.)
2h	—	—	—	(p.e.)	—	(p.e.)
2k	—	14 (p.i.)	20 (o.z.)	—	—	(p.e.)
3a	—	12 (o.z.)	—	—	—	(p.e.)
3b	—	12 (o.z.)	—	—	—	(p.e.)
4b	—	15 (o.z.)	—	—	—	(p.e.)
5a	—	—	—	15 (o.z.)	30 (o.z.)	—

a, R=p-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	—	13 (o.z.)	14 (o.z.)	—	13 (p.i.)	—
b, R=p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	—	13 (o.z.)	—	—	—	—
c; R=CH ₃	—	13 (o.z.)	—	18	25 (o.z.)	25 (o.z.)

* (p.e.)=Promotion effect, (p.i.)=partial inhibition, (o.z.)=clear zone.

electronic spectra on a Pye-Unicam SP 8000 spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched silica cells.

8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonylchloride (1)⁶: It was prepared by the action of chlorosulphonic acid on 8-hydroxyquinoline at a temperature not exceeding 15° and then left for 1 h. It was poured on

crushed ice with continuous stirring when 1 was separated immediately⁶.

7-Aryl(or alkyl)aminomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonamides (2-4): A mixture of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonamide (0.004 mol), paraformaldehyde (0.004 mol) and the primary or secondary

aromatic or aliphatic amine (0.008 mol) was refluxed for 30–40 h. The resulting solids were crystallised from acetic acid (60–70%). The compounds (Table 1) were found insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, dioxan, ether and acetone, moderately soluble in glacial acetic acid, sparingly soluble in ethanol and methanol and soluble in hot dilute HCl.

7-Substituted-aminomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-N-piperidylsulphonamide (5) A mixture of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonylchloride (0.004 mol) and piperidine (0.008 mol) was refluxed in ethanol for 2 h. The separated solid was crystallised from water as greenish pale yellow crystals, m.p. 324° (Found: C, 57.75; H, 5.64; N, 9.45; S, 10.80. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2S$ calcd. for C, 57.53; H, 5.48; N, 9.59; S, 10.96%).

A mixture of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-piperidylsulphonamide (0.004 mol) and the amine (0.004 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (50 ml) for 30 h. The separated solid was crystallised from water as buff coloured crystals of **5** (Table 1).

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